

The Gut-Wrenching Truth: Pathophysiology and Clinical Features of Intestinal Hyperpermeability Syndrome

Mohammad Salim ✉

Sanjay Gandhi Smriti Govt. Autonomous P.G. College Sidhi,
A.P.S. Univ. Rewa (MP), India

Vivek Kumar Singh

Sanjay Gandhi Smriti Govt. Autonomous P.G. College Sidhi,
A.P.S. Univ. Rewa (MP), India

Ram Gopal Singh

Sanjay Gandhi Smriti Govt. Autonomous P.G. College Sidhi,
A.P.S. Univ. Rewa (MP), India

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Abstract

The microbes associated with the gut are called the gut microbiota. There are about 1000 species of bacteria weighing up to 1-2 kg in the human gut. Microbial diversity increases with age until it is stable. Humans have evolved to live with them and have learned to play their role in the body. Dysbiosis in the gut microbiota causes various ailments, disorders and diseases in humans. And all of this is due to the increased intestinal permeability caused by gut microbiota dysbiosis. The present review discusses some pathophysiological and clinical symptoms of leaky gut syndrome, a highly controversial but logical and relevant topic of medical microbiology and gastroenterology in humans.

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Introduction

Leaky gut syndrome (LGS), also known as enhanced intestinal permeability is a condition that disrupts not only gut health but also affects other aspects of health as well. Although the leaky gut has not currently been recognized in medical diagnosis, studies have shown that people suffering from certain gastrointestinal diseases have some sort of leaky guts. And, physicians should be aware of these barrier dysfunctions in gastrointestinal disorders and their efficacy as a target for future therapy. This is a proposed digestive condition with enhanced intestinal permeability (IP) creating gaps in the intestinal walls. It allows various substances like food particles, microbes and waste products to seep directly into the bloodstream. This is all carried out with the help of tiny gaps in the tight junctions found in intestinal wall epithelial cells. It has already been reported that increased intestinal permeability plays a key role in producing certain gastrointestinal conditions in humans in association with other autoimmune diseases and mental illnesses. There are four major reasons for the leaky gut syndrome in humans. They are microbiome dysbiosis, poor diet, stress and toxins. There is growing- evidence

that dysbiosis of the gut microbiota is linked with disease development in humans. Both extraintestinal and gastrointestinal diseases are developed. These diseases are developed involving the pivotal mutualistic relationship between the colonic microbiota, their metabolic products and the immune responses developed. One of the most important evidence involved in the development of colorectal cancer with the use of very high protein diets and production of carcinogenic metabolites inducing neoplasia in the colonic epithelium [1-8]. Further, the article serves as a guide to the dynamics of the human gut microbiome explaining why this is so important for us. The present review is an attempt to discuss the leaky gut syndrome in connection with pathophysiological and clinical symptoms in light of recent research done so far in the fields of medical microbiology and gastroenterology. It deals with the study of some pathophysiological and clinical symptoms of leaky gut in humans are as gastrointestinal disorders, respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, kidney and bladder dysfunctions, fibromyalgia and joint pain, atopic dermatitis, hormonal imbalances, poor immunity, autoimmune disorders, allergy, neurological and

mental disorders. Some pathophysiological and clinical features developed due to intestinal hyperpermeability are discussed as under.

Changes in Gut Microbiota Developing Gastrointestinal Disorders

Recent trends in the study of gut microbiota have been linked to various gastrointestinal disorders. Extensive research has established human health by modulating the various physiological functions in the body. It has played a key role in safeguarding the integrity of the intestinal barrier, protecting from harmful bacteria with the development of immune responses. Similarly, the gut microbiota has consequently become an extremely important research area in gastroenterology. Some of the gastrointestinal diseases developed due to alterations in gut microbiota and *vice versa* are described as painful functional dyspepsia [9]; small intestinal bacterial overgrowth (SIBO), LIBO, SIFO, IMO and candidal overgrowth [10-12]; gas and bloating [10-12]; gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD); PPIs and hypochlorhydria [13-15]; appetite signaling disorder [16]; ulcerative colitis (UC) due to *Helicobacter pylori* and painful burning sensation in stomach [17]; constipation [18]; chronic diarrhea [19]; antibiotics associated diarrhoea [20]; metabolic syndrome (Wang *et al.* 2020) [21]; non alcoholic fatty disease (NAFLD) [22]; liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) [23]; esophageal disease (Ikenna *et al.* 2019) [24]; irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) [25,26]; irritable bowel disease (IBD) [27]; Crohn's disease [28] and colorectal cancer [23].

Changes in Gut Microbiota and Respiratory Diseases

Recently, an increasing amount of evidence indicated that there is a relationship between gut microbiota and common respiratory problems including bronchitis, asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), cystic fibrosis (CF), respiratory infections and lung cancer in human. [29-34]. COPD is a group of diseases including emphysema, bronchitis and asthmatic airway obstruction developing breathing problems in individuals. The patients suffering from COPD have been documented with the presence of *Streptococcus* sp000187445 and *Streptococcus vestibularis* correlating with reduced efficiency of lungs. It means lung activity is impacted by the activity of gut. The relative abundance of *Bacillus mimicus* and *Prevotella* is lower and higher in COPD patients respectively [35-36]. Asthma is a common chronic respiratory illness causing a larger number of morbidity and mortality in humans worldwide. It has been reported that gut microbiota dysbiosis played a key role in developing respiratory infections and asthma [37]. Similarly, microbial dysbiosis has also been linked to cystic fibrosis (CF). This is a severe genetic disease caused by the mutation in the CFTR gene resulting in the accumulation of sticky mucus in the lungs. It develops

insufficiency of hydration and bacterial infection [38,39].

Gut Microbiota Dysbiosis and Cardiovascular Diseases

Cardiovascular diseases mainly include atherosclerosis, heart failure and hypertension. Atherosclerotic diseases like acute coronary syndrome and stroke are correlated with the high occurrence of Enterobacteriaceae and *Streptococcus* spp. in gut microbiota. *Bacteroides*, *Clostridium* and Lactobacillales have been considered as a marker for patients suffering from coronary artery disease. Gut dysbiosis affects the cholesterol transport system (CTS) developing metabolic endotoxemia. Further, Trimethyl – amine N oxide levels are directly linked to the dysbiosis of gut microbiota it can impair the functioning of reverse cholesterol transport (RCT) developing cardiovascular diseases at risk. The short chain fatty acids (SCFAs) lower blood pressure by binding the olfactory receptors found in the heart and blood vessels, kidney and sympathetic ganglia [40-43].

Changes in Gut Microbiota, Kidney and Bladder Dysfunction

The microbiota is a complex network of microorganisms interconnected in the human body. The gut microbiota maintains its relationship with various organs of the body including the urinogenital tract with a dynamic equilibrium. The urinary tract has its specific microbiota. When the gut kidney axis microbiome is disturbed, various diseases like kidney injury, chronic kidney diseases and nephropathy have appeared with the production of uremic compounds and toxins. Several studies have shown that gut bacteria are involved in kidney diseases in humans. A metabolite known as uremic retention solute as p-Cresyl (p-CS) has been identified and circulating in the blood of patients suffering from chronic kidney disease. It has been documented that the gut microbiota produces p-CS. The p-CS might be used as an identification marker for chronic kidney diseases in humans. Further, sometimes the bladder-intestine-brain axis due to the dysbiosis of gut microbiota also created pathophysiology of disorders developing the clinical signs and symptoms of bladder dysfunction [44,45].

Fibromyalgia, CFS and Joint Pain

Clinically, the pains developed due to changes in gut microbiota are fibromyalgia, chronic fatigue syndrome and arthritis [44,46]. The prestigious journal "Pain" has for the first time published the link between changes in gut microbiota and the development of fibromyalgia in humans. Patients suffering from fibromyalgia have documented higher levels of *Clostridium*, *Bacteroides*, *Ruminococcus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Eubacterium* and *Firmicutes* [47]. Similarly, changes in gut microbiota might be a signature of chronic fatigue syndrome (CFS) or myalgic encephalomyelitis (ME) [46].

Chronic fatigue syndrome (CFS) or Myalgic encephalomyelitis (ME) is a serious, debilitating and chronic disease characterized by several symptoms including abdominal pain, nausea, constipation or diarrhoea, fatigue, post-exertional malaise, sleep disorder and body pain. It has been observed that the CFS patients' microbiota is different from healthy controls. Decreased microbial diversity of *Firmicutes* and *Faecalibacterium* and an increased number of *Alistipes* were found as a top biomarker of CFS/ME. It has been observed that good butyrate-producing bacteria responsible for the breakdown of the fibres of food like *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and *Eubacterium rectale* are reduced in subjects with CFS [46-48].

Further, gout is a disease of elevated uric acid in the blood due to the purine metabolism disorder. High level of uric acid in blood leads to the crystallization and accumulation of uric acid crystals in joints causing acute pain. A gout patient when examined was found to have *Bacteroides caccae* and *Bacteroides xylanisolveris* developing serious inflammatory responses. Simultaneously, the beneficial bacteria *Bifidobacterium pseudocatenulatum* producing butyrate, a product good for gut health was found less in amount [44]. Lastly, there are various types of arthritis found in humans such as arthritis and joint pain [49], psoriatic arthritis (PSA) [50], rheumatoid arthritis (RA) [51] and osteoarthritis (OA) [52].

Atopic Dermatitis

Studies have shown that gut dysbiosis precedes the onset of atopic dermatitis. Increasing evidence suggested that alterations in gut microbiota sometimes developed various skin diseases like psoriasis, eczema, acne and lichen planus. It has been described as the skin-gut axis. Most of the articles agree that *Bifidobacterium*, *Proteobacteria* and *Enterobacteria* played an anti-inflammatory effect in human [53,54]. The dysbiosis of the skin microbiome produces eczema in human. Colonization of *Staphylococcus aureus* has increased the severity of disease. Eczema, the most common form of atopic dermatitis have a less diverse gut microbiota. Research also suggests that a very specific type of gut microbiota is found in persons suffering from eczema. *Clostridium difficile* and *Escherichia coli* have been associated with the development of atopic dermatitis. Similarly, certain species of *Bifidobacterium* like *B. catenulatum*, *B. bifidum* and *B. pseudocatenulatum* are found in greater abundance in eczema patients [53-55].

Changes in Gut Microbiota Developing Hormonal Imbalances

There is a link between gut microbiota and hormones. The gut microbiome produces certain hormones like dopamine playing a key role in the regulation of estrogen. Imbalances in gut bacteria may contribute to hormonal disturbances affecting overall health and

well-being. Gut microbiota also influences sex hormones along with other metabolites. Some of the hormonal disturbances caused by the changes in gut microbiota in humans are hormonal imbalances [56,57]; sexual dimorphism disorder [57]; polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) [58]; premenstrual syndrome (PMS) [59]; endometriosis [61]; Diabetes [62,63] and sexual disorder and reproductive, metabolic and neuroendocrine Disorders [64-66].

Poor Immunity, Autoimmune Disorders and Allergy

With the rising prevalence of autoimmune diseases microbial dysbiosis and the role of leaky gut have become an extraordinary platform for the same study. Certain autoimmune diseases are influenced by dysbiosis in gut microbiota. It appears that the gut microbiota is closely involved in autoimmune pathogenesis. Might be this due to the ability of gut microbiota involved in autoimmune pathogenesis to alter the intestinal barrier in humans. Some of the autoimmune disorders involved in leaky gut syndrome are as multiple sclerosis (MS) [67,68], vitiligo [69], systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) [70], autoimmune diseases [71] and allergic rhinitis [72].

Further, imbalances in gut microbiota have also been reported to cause abnormal immune responses and subsequently allergic diseases. Studies have shown that people with allergies have a less diverse gut microbiome. People suffering from irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) have been reported to have *klebsiella aerogenes* in their gut producing histamines. Similarly, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* can lead to the release of increased histamines. Some of the allergies developed due to changes in gut microbiota are as allergic diseases [73], food allergy [74,75], food sensitivity [76], histamine intolerance and asthma [77,78], allergic mycotoxins (Winnie and Sabran 2018) [79], lactose intolerance [80], celiac disease [81] and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) [82].

Changes in Gut Microbiota Developing Neurological and Mental Disorders

Alterations in gut microbiota and dysbiosis also produce neuronal and mental disorders in humans. These diseases are developed due to harmful microbial metabolite production, disturbed immune responses and neurodegeneration occurring in the human body. Brain dysfunctions are due to the specific alterations of gut microbiota by modulating serotonergic, noradrenergic, dopaminergic, glutamatergic and GABA-ergic neurotransmission. Emerging evidence indicates that the changes in gut microbiota play a key role in modulating neurotransmission and communicating the brain signals to affect the pathophysiology of neuropsychiatric and neurological disorders in humans. Some of the neuropsychiatric and neurological disorders as influenced by gut dysbiosis in humans are as depression [82]; anxiety [82]; insomnia [82];

migraine [83]; autism [84]; stress [85]; attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) [86]; difficulty in concentration and dementia [87]; neurological diseases [88]; neuropsychiatric disorders [5]; brain disorders [89]; brain stroke [90]; Alzheimer's disease (AD) [91]; Parkinson's disease (PD) (Wood 2023) [92] and schizophrenia [93].

Conclusion

The microorganisms that live in the gut are referred to as the gut microbiota composed of various microorganisms like bacteria, fungi and viruses. There are about 100 trillion bacterial cells, outnumbering the human cells by an estimated 10X and the human genome by 150X. They have evolved to co-exist in the gut in a mutualistic relationship performing various functions related to nutrition, immune responses and the protection from infections by pathogenic bacterial species. And, in turn, the human body provides shelter and mucus for nutrition to them. Changes in gut microbiota causing dysbiosis developed various diseases in humans. The present paper focuses on the association of gut microbiota with several gastrointestinal disorders, hormonal imbalances, allergy, fibromyalgia and joint pain, atopic dermatitis, poor immunity and autoimmune disorders, cancer, respiratory and cardiovascular dysfunctions, kidney and bladder dysfunctions, sexual dysfunction and neural and mental disorders in human. The present paper is framed to better understand the mechanisms involved in the development of diseases due to the dysbiosis of gut microbiota, though they are largely unnoticed.

Abbreviations

ME	Myalgic encephalomyelitis
MS	Multiple sclerosis
CF	Cystic fibrosis
UC	Ulcerative colitis
RA	Rheumatoid arthritis
IP	Intestinal permeability
RA	Rheumatoid arthritis
AD	Alzheimer's disease
PD	Parkinson's disease
OA	Osteoarthritis
P-CS	P-Cresyl
LGS	Leaky gut syndrome
CTS	Cholesterol transport system
GIT	Gastrointestinal tract
RCT	Reverse cholesterol transport
IBS	Irritable bowel syndrome
HMP	Human Microbiome project
CNS	Central nervous system
PMS	Premenstrual syndrome
IBD	Inflammatory bowel disease
CFS	Chronic fatigue syndrome
SLE	Systemic lupus erythematosus
PSA	Psoriatic arthritis

IMO	Intestinal methanogen overgrowth
GERD	Gastroesophageal reflux disease
PCOS	Polycystic ovary syndrome
ADHD	Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder
SIBO	Small intestine bacterial overgrowth
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
NAFLD	Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease
SCFA	Short chain fatty acid
CDSA	Comprehensive Digestive Stool Analysis
PPIs	Proton pump inhibitors
SIFO	Small intestinal fungal overgrowth
LIBO	Larger intestinal bacterial overgrowth
CFTR gene	Cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator gene
GABA- argic	Gamma-aminobutyric acid-argic system

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Ethical clearance

As this is purely a review article, therefore, it does not require any ethical clearance.

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